
EFFECT OF ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE ON THE PERFORMANCE OF FOOD AND BEVERAGE MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN ENUGU STATE

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ABSTRACT: The study evaluated the effect of organisational culture on the employee performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state. The specific objectives of the study were to: evaluate the effect of transformational leadership culture on the employee punctuality and ascertain the effect of shared values on the employee punctuality of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state. The descriptive survey design was used. The study adopted simple sampling technique in selecting the sample unit and the sample size for the study which was, 250 staff out of a total population of 715 employees derived with the use of Freund Williams formula. A total of 241 staff returned the questionnaire accurately filled. Data were presented and analyzed using mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using the Z - test. The findings indicated that transformational leadership culture had significant positive effect on the employee punctuality $Z = 5.604 < 8.696$, $P. < .05$ and Shared values had significant positive effect on the employee punctuality of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state, $Z = 6.442 < 8.938$, $P. < .05$. The study concluded that Transformational leadership culture and shared values had significant positive effect on the employee punctuality of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state. The study recommended among others that to ensure employees to demonstrate their creativity and innovative ability there is need to encourage Transformational leaders. They become role models for employees, often inspiring them to follow in their footsteps.

Keywords: Employee performance, organisational culture, leadership culture, shared values.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Organizational Culture is the pattern of shared basic assumptions that was learned by a group as it solved its problems of external adaptation and internal integration (Schein, 2017). These assumptions are said to be maintained in the continuous process of human interaction (attitudes and behavior) as the right way in which things are done (Zhang & Pan, 2019) also describes OC as a mode, composed by some basic assumptions; and the assumptions are found and created gradually by a certain group in the process of exploring the method of adapting to external environment and solving internal interconnected system. Organizational culture plays a vital role in ensuring performance of employees and organization. Organizational culture entails values, beliefs,

and practices which constitute the characteristics of an organization according to Gostick and Elton (2017). It is, therefore, a system of shared values that interacts with staff, structure, and control system of an organization as indicated by Rock (2016). It, therefore, defines behavioral norms of employee which lead to productivity of employee.

Organizational culture is also called corporate culture. Organizational culture is the combination of expectations of organization, experiences, philosophy and values. Organizational culture influences on performance and productivity of organization. It gives guidelines for quality of product, punctuality, safety and other factor affecting on environment. Organizational culture is unusual for every organization and it is very problematic to change it (Raduan, 2020).

The culture of any organization has been considered the decisive factor in it shaping and has an immense effect on the structure and design of an organization, internal and external environment of an organization, technology, work force and more importantly on the efficiency and strategy of an organization. A rich organizational culture, just like productive energy, guides the organization by its efficient work force, directs the emotions and perceptions towards a shared goal, increases motivation, creates creativity and intimacy in the organization's environment, and systematizes everything.

The performance of employees improves by establishing a strong culture in an organization (Awadh & Saad, 2018). Raduan (2020) observes that, a high degree of productivity is related a culture with well integrated and effective set of values, beliefs and behaviors. A strong organizational culture can function as a reliable compass and a powerful tool for guiding and modifying the organizational productivity of manufacturing firms. In today's competitive business environment the main challenge is about having reliable and high performance human resources. Therefore, OC is important to organizational performance (Twati & Gammack, 2016).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

A company with a clear organisational culture will easily be able to align new starters with the company's goals and values. They will have a clear set of practices and beliefs. This will encourage new starters to adhere to their processes and rules of engagement. Organizational culture helps improve workflows and guides the decision-making process. It also helps teams overcome barriers of ambiguity. Team members who are informed and knowledgeable about certain processes are often more motivated to finish projects.

Poor company culture has affected the organisations because leaders have created an environment where communication is poor, there is a focus on profit (not on employees) and hyper-competition, micromanagement or bullying behaviour exist. The challenges of transformational leadership culture and poor shared values

Lack of organisational culture can lead to low employee morale, lack of employee punctuality and output, decreased productivity, and high staff turnover. It can also harm the firm's reputation, impact customer satisfaction, and ultimately negatively affect profitability and growth. The study therefore is carried out to evaluate the effect of organisational culture on the employee performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study was to evaluate the effect of organisational culture on the employee performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state. The specific objectives of the study were to:

i. Evaluate the effect of transformational leadership culture on the employee punctuality of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

ii. Ascertain the effect of shared values on the employee punctuality-of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

i. What is the effect of transformational leadership culture on the employee punctuality of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state?

ii. What is the effect of shared values on the employee punctuality of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state?

1.5 Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study:

i. Transformational leadership culture has effect on the employee punctuality of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

ii. Shared values have effect on the employee punctuality of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Organisation

An organization is an entity such as a company, an institution, or an association comprising one or more people and having a particular purpose. The word is derived from the Greek word organon, which means tool or instrument, musical instrument, and organ. There are a variety of legal types of organizations, including corporations, governments, non-governmental organizations, political organizations, international organizations, armed forces, charities, not-for-profit corporations, partnerships, cooperatives, and educational institutions etc. A hybrid organization is a body that operates in both the public sector and the private sector simultaneously, fulfilling public duties and developing commercial market activities (Lui & Ngo Hang-Y, 2014).

2.1.2 Culture

Culture is a set of customs, values, norms and beliefs that influence on an organization There are different personalities in organization. Organization can be taken as humanity, warmth, wise, and modernism and have special characters like these. In organization these characters are used to predict the employee's behavior (Khorshidi, 2019). Culture comes from a culture of organization but it is not the culture of society. In each organization beliefs, attitudes and pattern of culture are influenced. Farjad (2018) believed that culture have two parts that are material culture which involve all facilities, buildings etc. and spiritual and immaterial culture which includes values, laws, customs, arts and philosophies.

2.1.3 Organizational Culture

Organizational culture is a collective behavior of people that are part of an organization. It is formed by the organization values, visions, norms, working language, systems, and symbols, beliefs and habits. It is also the pattern of such collective behaviors and assumptions that are taught to new organizational members as a way of

perceiving, and even thinking and feeling. Organizational cultures affect the way people and groups interact with each other, with clients, and with stakeholders (Schein, 2019). Organizational Culture is a strength that can be a weakness. It is strength because it eases and economizes communication, facilitates organizational decision making and control and may generate higher levels of cooperation and commitment to the organization which are necessary for strategy implementation. (Pearce, 2016).

2.1.4 Components of Organisational culture used in the Study

2.1.4.1 Transformational Leadership Culture

Transformational leadership is a process in which the leaders took actions to try to increase their followers' awareness of what was right and important. This process was associated with motivating followers to perform "beyond expectation" and encouraging followers to look beyond their own self-interest for the good of the group or organisation. By working harder for a transformational leader, his or her followers could develop their skills by using their own decisions and taking greater responsibility (Yukl, 2018). Transformational leaders are typically described as those who inspire their followers to adopt goals and values that are consistent with the leader's vision.

2.1.4.2 Shared Values

Shared values are organizational values that are usually developed by the organization's leadership and then adopted by the other members of the organization. The values are shared and followed by all members of the organization when acting on behalf of the organization. They may also be referred to as core values. Creating and implementing shared values is important for all organizations. They provide guidance for organizational decision-making and also provide a kind of ethical compass for organizational action (Shared Values in an Organization: Definition & Explanation, 2016).

2.1.5 Employee

An employee is an individual who was hired by an employer to do a specific job (Heathfield, 2021). An employee is an individual that is hired to work for a person or company that pays them a wage or salary in return (Lord, 2021). Employee is someone who works for another person who controls what is to be done and how the job is performed. John provides the store, inventory, and equipment for the employees to do their job. Employees at his store are required to wear uniforms and work when they are scheduled. All the employee has to do is show up to work on time and prepared and do his or her job as instructed (Lord, 2021).

2.1.6 Performance

Organizational performance is the valued productive output of a system in the form of goods or services. Organizational performance can be subdivided into three categories: financial performance internal non-financial performance and external non-financial performance. Entrepreneurs strive for good financial results whereas public organizations are aimed at non-financial aims like delivering good public services to citizens. To achieve performance through employees, the organization must consider them as assets and must be treated with attention so that the employees become productive (Kimani, 2016).

2.1.6.1 Employee performance

In view of Deadrick and Gardner's (2017) points, employee performance could be defined as the record of outcomes achieved, for each job function, during a specified period of time, performance is represented as a

distribution of outcomes achieved, and performance could be measured by using a variety of parameters which describe an employee's pattern of performance over time. Employee performance is directly based on employees' productivity via an assessment of factors such as quality, quantity and effectiveness of work as well as employees behavior in the workplace (Chukwuma, 2020).

Components of Employee performance

i. Employee Punctuality

Punctuality aims at ensuring that employees attend office daily and also complete their working hours. Punctual employees are valuable assets to any organization that wants to be performance. Employees who do not respect punctuality constitute mere burdens on the system and do not contribute much to the overall productivity of the organization. Managers need to ensure that their employees reach office on time and do not unnecessarily sit till late (White, 2012). It is asserted that leaving on time and coming back fresh and completely recharged the next day is more profitable for the organization.

2.1.7 Conceptual Framework of the Study

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by dynamic capabilities, by Teece (1997)

2.2.1 Dynamic Capabilities Theory

According to Teece et al. (1997), Dynamic Capabilities is defined as “the firm’s ability to integrate, build and reconfigure internal and external competencies to address rapidly changing environments”. Dynamic Capabilities allow corporations to develop and assign resources that sustain efficient business performance (Teece et al., 1997; Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Teece, 2007). Similarly, Eisenhardt and Martin (2000) defines Dynamic Capabilities as organizational practices that integrate, reconfigure, acquire and distribute resources in the quest for competitive advantages that would help to create flexibility in responding to market changes. Dynamic capabilities constitutes a system of resources which enterprises can integrate, reconfigure, remodel and assign for the purposes of achieving competitive advantage (Ludwig & Pemberton, 2011 cited in (Bleady & Ali, 2018). It is a set of configurable resources which a firm can utilize for the process of adapting in the business environment characterized by changes (Simon, Stockport, Smith, Klobas & Sohal, 2015).

From the definition above, it is generally agreed that for a resource to be dynamically capable of responding to market changes, it must be readily configurable, adaptive, and transferable in order to respond adequately and timely to external conditions that may affect business’s performance.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 Transformational leadership culture on the Employee Punctuality

Kittikunchotiwut (2020) carried out a study on Transformational Leadership and Financial Performance: The Mediating Roles of Learning Orientation and Firm Innovativeness examine the relationships between transformational leadership, learning orientation, firm innovativeness, and financial performance. Specifically, the moderating effect of learning orientation and firm innovativeness. The data collected from 606 SMEs in

Thailand were evaluated using the structural equation modeling, typifying that quantitative research. The results revealed that transformational leadership had a positive effect on learning orientation. Similarly, transformational leadership had a positive effect on firm innovativeness. Further, the study found that transformational leadership had a positive indirect effect on financial performance through the mediation of learning orientation. The results of the study found that transformational leadership had a positive indirect effect on financial performance through the mediation of firm innovativeness. Transformational leadership and learning orientation to improve innovation within the organization, including organizations and leaders among themselves.

Masta & Riyanto (2020) carried out a study on the Effect of Transformational Leadership, Perceived Organizational Support and Workload on Turnover Intention Sharia Banking Company in Jakarta. The purpose of this study was to look at the Transformational Leadership effect, Perceived Organizational Support, and Workload on Turnover Intention in one of sharia banking in Jakarta. Samples of the study were employees who worked at one of sharia banking in Jakarta. Sampling was conducted using nonprobability techniques, which is purposive sampling with the Slovin formula of 101 people. This study was conducted quantitatively, and the analysis method used in this study was multiple linear regression analysis. The results of the study showed that transformational leadership, perceived organizational support and workload variables have a significant effect on turnover intention. The result of the study also showed that what affects turnover intention the most is workload. It was proven by the results of the simultaneous test (F test) and partial test (t-test) which showed the numerous value of three independent variables that supported the hypothesis.

Rafia, Sudiro and Sunaryo (2020) examined and analyzed the effect between transformational leadership and employee's performance on the Civil Servants of Public Housing and Settlement Areas of Central Java Province, both directly and through job satisfaction and employee engagement. This research was use a quantitative research methods and belongs to a type of explanatory research. A sample was all Civil Servants of the Department of Public Housing and Settlement Areas of Central Java Province who actively worked totaling 77 respondents. The sampling technique has been used with saturated or census samples. Data were analyzed using PLS (Partial Least Square) with the Smart PLS 3.0 program. The results were indicated that transformational leadership does not have a direct significant effect on employee performance, but has a direct significant effect on job satisfaction and employee engagement.

Rawashdeh, Almasarweh, Alhyasat and Al-Rawashdeh (2021) investigated the effect of transformational leadership to organisational performance via the mediating role of quality innovation in Jordan. Adopting a quantitative research design, data were collected from 222 middle level- leaders using a self-structured questionnaire. Structural equation modeling (SEM) via The Analysis of Moment Structures, i.e., IBM AMOS 22 was used to test the hypotheses. The findings indicated that transformational leadership was significantly associated with both innovation and organisational performance. Furthermore, innovation has a positive effect on organisational performance. Consequently, the results underlined a significant mediation role of innovation in the relationship between transformational leadership and organisational performance. The findings of this study serve as a guide for leaders and policymakers in terms of having better understanding on the relationship between transformational leadership, quality innovation, and organisational performance.

2.3.2 Effect of shared values on the Employee punctuality

Raza, Burney and Ahsanullah (2019) conducted a study to determine the service quality impacts on customer satisfaction of the banking sector of Pakistan. Five hundred customers of three sub-sectors of commercial banks in the i) private-sector, ii) public-sector, and iii) the Islamic-banks were questioned on the Weighted SERVPERF model. The validity and reliability of the data have been tested using CFA and SEM, with the study analysed using descriptive research design and Chi-square. The analysis confirmed that service quality with its

five dimensions has a significant and positive impact on customer satisfaction. Based on overall mean of data, a comparative analysis of three sub-sectors was carried out to distinguish between high and low quality of their service performance. The findings indicate that private-sector conventional banks are distinguished as high-performance agents followed by Islamic-banks both in public and private sectors, whereas the public-sector conventional banks are shown as low-performance banking services.

Egdair and Abdelsalam (2020) investigated the impact of the corporate culture on the service quality of Islamic banks in Libya. Additionally, the study has also investigated the mediating role of work engagement. The study used a survey-based method where the close ended questionnaires were structured. For the collection of quantitative data, we have distributed questionnaires among the respondents. To test the hypothesis of this study we have used Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). We have distributed total 538 questionnaires, whereas 412 questionnaires were received back. Total 15 questionnaires were dropped because of missing information. The total useable questionnaires were 397, and the response rate for the present study was 76.6%. This aim of this paper is to review previous studies that addressed the phenomena of organisational culture in several organisations, and what their impact it on service quality. Organisational culture as a social phenomenon has been studied in previous studies to find deficiencies in this field and to examine the future research focus on this issue. However, concern the issue of organisational culture on service quality still unconsidered and require more in-depth studies especially in Libya.

Metz, Ilies and Nistor (2020) conducted study focused on a multinational ITC (Information Technology and Communications) company in Romania. Empirical research aimed to evaluate organisational culture based on Denison's model through four features: capacity development, basic values, customer orientation, and goals and objectives. At the same time, the study analyzed service provided to customers, taking into account its three phases: pre-transaction, transaction, and post-transaction. The empirical study is based on a homogenous sample made up of 215 members of the analysed company, whose representativeness is provided by the fact that all employees (managers and employees without managerial functions) directly involved in the design, implementation, operationalization, and monitoring of customer service are included. As research methods, the researchers used a questionnaire-based survey and direct observation. The results of the study demonstrate that the company has a strong culture based on an adequate core value system (shared by company members), innovative and effective human capital management practices, and customer orientation. All characteristics ensure the integration of sustainability principles into strategies, policies, and management practices of the company.

Jamaludin, Azhar, Salizawatee and Jamil (2021) examined the important contributions of employees' Personal Values on organisational Commitment especially in construction Industry in Malaysia where there is paucity of research in this area. The independent variables are Personal Values (Stimulation, Universalism, Achievement, Self-Direction and Benevolence). The dependent variable is the Organisational Commitment (Affective Commitment, Continuance Commitment and Normative Commitment). The sampling frame (N=160) is concentrated on the technical foreign workers who work in Construction Industry Development Board (CIDB). The data was analysed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences²⁵ (SPSS 25) by applying the method of descriptive statistics. Results show that Achievement values and Self-Direction values are proven to have important influences on organisational Commitment. This study discusses the results from the social, psychological, and human resource perspectives, as well as their implications for human resource management.

2.4 Gap in Empirical Review

The studies done were carried outside the effect of organisational culture on the employee performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the transformational leadership culture on the employee punctuality; shared values on the employee punctuality-of

food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state. Most of the studies reviewed analysed their data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method, Simple linear regression and Pearson correlation coefficient (r) while the present study made use of Z test to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the effect of organisational culture on the employee performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

METHODOLOGY

The area of the study was Enugu state, Nigeria. The selected food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state include: B O MBA Ind., food chemicals Ltd, Old airport Road, Emene, Bons Ind. Ltd, KM 2, Ontisha-Enugu Express; Omo foodstuff, plot 62 RCC Estate, JUHEL Limited, Nkworogba, Emene. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. The actual population was seven hundred and fifteen employees (715). To determine the adequate sample size of 250, the study opted for the Freund and Williams (1986) statistical formula at 5% margin of error. Out of the sample size of 250 distribute, Two hundred and forty one (241) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 96.4 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.810 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z - test statistic tool.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSES

This section presents and analyzes the data collected for the study.

4.1 Data Presentation

4.1.1 The effect of transformational leadership culture on the employee punctuality of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state

Table 4.1.1.1: Responses on the effect of transformational leadership culture on the employee punctuality of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Transformational leadership promotes motivation that helps employee come to work on time	435 87 36.1	80 20 8.3	219 73 30.3	78 39 16.2	22 22 9.1	834 241 100.0	3.46	1.360	Agree
2	Effective transformational leadership helps maintain work place integrity and gingers employees coming	625 125 51.9	80 20 8.3	117 39 16.2	62 31 12.9	26 26 10.8	910 241 100.0	3.78	1.458	Agree
3	There is decrease employee turnover and improvement in employee loyalty transformational leadership	525 105 43.8	80 20 8.3	183 61 25.4	52 26 10.8	28 28 11.7	868 241 100.0	3.60	1.427	Agree
4	Transformational leaders work to bring about human and economic transformation	570 114 47.3	176 44 18.3	99 33 13.7	52 26 10.8	24 24 10.0	921 241 100.0	3.82	1.383	Agree
5	Good transformational leaders defines a dear vision and goal and it promotes employees to be punctual	675 135 56.0	148 37 15.4	66 22 9.1	52 26 10.8	21 21 8.7	962 241 100.0	3.99	1.369	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								18.65	6.997	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4.1.1.1, 107 respondents out of 241 representing 44,4 percent agreed that Transformational leadership promotes motivation that helps employee come to work on time with mean score 3.46 and standard deviation of 1360. 145 respondents representing 60.2 percent agreed that Effective transformational leadership helps maintain work place integrity and gingers employees coming with mean score of 3.78 and standard deviation of 1.458. 125respondents representing 52.1 percent agreed that There is decrease employee turnover and improvement in employee loyalty transformational leadership with mean score of 3.60 and standard deviation of 1.427. 158 respondents representing 65.6 percent agreed that Transformational leaders work to bring about human and economic transformation with mean score of 3.82 and standard deviation of 1.383. 172 respondents representing 71.4 percent agreed that Good transformational leaders defines a dear vision and goal and it promotes employees to be punctual with a mean score of 3.99 and standard deviation 1.369.

4.1.2 The effect of shared values on the employee punctuality employee output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state

Table 4.1.2.1: Responses on the effect of shared values on the employee punctuality employee output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Shared value foster sense of belonging within employees that enhances productivity	500 100 41.5	220 55 22.8	54 18 7.5	84 42 17.4	26 26 10.8	884 241 100.0	3.67	1.434	Agree
2	Employee align with an organizations values it promotes growth	545 109 45.2	320 80 33.2	57 19 7.9	26 13 5.4	20 20 8.3	968 241 100.0	4.02	1.225	Agree
3	Experiencing higher job satisfaction and commitment are promoted through shared values	680 136 56.4	252 63 26.1	54 18 7.5	12 6 2.5	18 18 7.5	1016 241 100.0	4.22	1.170	Agree
4	Values help employee to understand their purposes within the organization	595 119 49.4	308 77 32.0	39 13 5.4	36 18 7.5	14 14 5.8	992 241 100.0	4.12	1.167	Agree
5	The shared value promotes a picture work culture and employees feel connected to the organization.	410 82 34.0	388 97 40.2	39 13 5.4	64 32 13.3	17 17 7.1	918 241 100%	3.81	1.237	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								19.84	6.233	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4.1.2.1, 155 respondents out of 241 representing 437.8 percent agreed that Shared value foster sense of belonging within employees that enhances productivity with mean score 3.67 and standard deviation of 1.434. 189 respondents representing 78.4 percent agreed that Employee align with an organization values it promotes growth with mean score of 4.02 and standard deviation of 1.225. 199 respondents representing 82.5 percent agreed with mean score of 4.22 and standard deviation of 1.170. 196 respondents representing 81.4 percent agreed that Values help employee to understand their purposes within the organization with mean score of 4.12 and 1.167. 179 respondents representing 74.2 percent agreed that the shared value promotes a picture work culture and employees feel connected to the organization, with a mean score of 3.81and standard deviation 1.237.

4.2 Test of hypotheses

4.2.1 Hypothesis One: Transformational leadership culture has effect on the employee punctuality of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Transformational leadership promotes motivation that helps employee come to work on time	Effective transformational leadership helps maintain work place integrity and gingers employees coming	There is decrease employee turnover and improvement in employee loyalty and transformational leadership	Transformational leaders work to bring about human and economic transformation	Good transformational leaders defines a dear vision and goal and it promotes employees to be punctual
N		241	241	240	241	241
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.361	.519	.438	.473	.560
	Positive	.091	.108	.117	.100	.087
	Negative	-.361	-.519	-.438	-.473	-.560
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		5.604	8.052	6.778	7.343	8.696
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from $5.604 < 8.696$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that **Transformational leadership culture had significant positive effect on the employee punctuality of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state.**

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $5.604 < 8.696$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that **Transformational leadership culture had significant positive effect on the employee punctuality of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state.**

4.2.2 Hypothesis Two: Shared values have effect on the employee output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Shared value foster sense of belonging within employees that enhances productivity	Employee align with organizations values promotes growth	Experiencing higher job satisfaction and commitment are promoted through shared values	Values help employee to understand their purposes within the organization	The shared value promotes a picture work culture and employees feel connected to the organization.
N		241	241	241	241	241
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.415	.534	.576	.563	.493
	Positive	.108	.083	.075	.058	.071
	Negative	-.415	-.534	-.576	-.563	-.493
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		6.442	8.294	8.938	8.744	7.649
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e. $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from $6.442 < 8.938$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that **Shared values had significant positive effect on the employee output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state.**

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $6.442 < 8.938$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that **Shared values had significant positive effect on the employee output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state.**

4.3 Discussion of Findings

4.3.1 Transformational leadership culture had significant positive effect on the employee punctuality of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

From the result of the hypothesis one, the calculated Z- value ranges from $5.604 < 8.696$ against the critical Z- value of .000 which implies that Transformational leadership culture had significant positive effect on the employee punctuality of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state. In the support of result of the result in the literature review, Kittikunchotiwut (2020) carried out a study on Transformational Leadership and Financial Performance. The results of the study found that transformational leadership had a positive indirect effect on financial performance through the mediation of firm innovativeness. Transformational leadership and learning orientation to improve innovation within the organization, including organizations and leaders among themselves. Masta & Riyanto (2020) carried out a study on the Effect of Transformational Leadership, Perceived Organizational Support and Workload on Turnover Intention Sharia Banking Company in Jakarta. The result of the study also showed that what affects turnover intention the most is workload.

4.3.2 Shared values had effect on the employee output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

From the result of the hypothesis two, the calculated Z- value ranges from $6.442 < 8.938$ against the critical Z- value of .000 which implies that Shared values had significant positive effect on the employee output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state. In the support of result of the result in the literature review, Egdair and Abdelsalam (2020) investigated the impact of the corporate culture on the service quality of Islamic banks in Libya. Organisational culture as a social phenomenon has been studied in previous studies to find deficiencies in this field and to examine the future research focus on this issue. However, concern the issue of organisational culture on service quality still unconsidered and require more in-depth studies especially in Libya. Metz, Ilies and Nistor (2020) conducted study focused on a multinational ITC (Information Technology and Communications) company in Romania. The results of the study demonstrate that the company has a strong culture based on an adequate core value system (shared by company members),

innovative and effective human capital management practices, and customer orientation. All characteristics ensure the integration of sustainability principles into strategies, policies, and management practices of the company.

5.0 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

- i. Transformational leadership culture had significant positive effect on the employee punctuality of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state, $Z = 5.604 < 8.696$, $P. < .05$.
- ii. Shared values had significant positive effect on the employee output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state, $Z = 6.442 < 8.938$, $P. < .05$.

5.2 Conclusion

The study concluded that Transformational leadership culture and shared values had significant positive effect on the employee punctuality of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state. Organisations that value relationships will be focused on building a culture where people work collaboratively and feel supported by their managers and leadership teams. Conversely, others may have a competitive mindset and have a more hierarchical structure that prioritizes more formal or financial motivations. Relationships feed directly into the emotional brain style and how important this is to a team will depend on their predominant brain type

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

- i. To ensure employees demonstrate their creativity and innovative ability, there is need for more encouragement of Transformational leaders. They become role models for employees, often inspiring them to follow in their footsteps.
- ii. There are six key benefits to creating shared value opportunities: To promote higher productivity, more innovation, faster and better decisions, lower costs, higher returns, and better relations the management of food and beverage firms should create more room for shared value opportunities.

5.4 Contribution to Knowledge

The studies done were carried outside the effect of organisational culture on the employee performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the transformational leadership culture on the employee punctuality, shared values on the employee output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state. Most of the studies reviewed analysed their data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method, Simple linear regression and Pearson correlation coefficient (r) while the present study made use of Z test to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the effect of organisational culture on the employee performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

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